
Examining the Socioeconomic Barriers to Implementing Nature-based Solutions (NbS) in Northwest Nigeria

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Abstract

This research examined the Socioeconomic barriers to implementing Nature-based Solutions (NbS) in Northwest Nigeria, specifically in Sokoto, Zamfara, and Katsina States. Utilising political ecology theory as a framework, a mixed-methods approach was employed, incorporating a survey of 700 participants (with 684 responses deemed valid) and focus group discussions involving stakeholders. Descriptive statistics identified poverty (50.3%), insecurity and conflict (36%), and lack of awareness (13.7%) as the primary barriers to the adoption of NbS. Chi-square tests revealed significant correlations between education, income, occupation, and perceived barriers ($p < 0.05$). Qualitative results supported these findings, with respondents noting that insecurity is a significant hindrance to agricultural activities, poverty limits environmental investments, and a lack of awareness represents a cultural and knowledge gap. The combined findings highlight that interconnected socioeconomic, political, and security factors influence the adoption of NbS in fragile environments. The study concludes that without addressing poverty, insecurity, and gaps in awareness, NbS initiatives will fail to achieve sustainability. It suggests policy reforms, support for livelihoods, security improvements, awareness initiatives, and collaboration among multiple stakeholders. This research contributes to the understanding of NbS barriers in conflict-impacted areas and offers evidence-based strategies for bolstering climate resilience in Nigeria.

Keywords: Nature-based Solutions (NbS); Climate Change; Poverty; Insecurity; Awareness; Political Ecology; Northwest Nigeria.

1. Introduction

Climate change presents a significant danger to both ecosystems and human societies worldwide, with its impacts disproportionately affecting the most vulnerable regions (Yakubu et al., 2025). Northwest Nigeria, noted for its semi-arid climate and agricultural reliance, is especially vulnerable to the detrimental consequences of climate variability (Abiola et al., 2025). Nature-based Solutions (NbS) have emerged as a viable strategy to enhance climate resilience by leveraging the capabilities of natural processes and ecosystems. The region has been experiencing increasing variability in climate, as evidenced by more severe and inconsistent rainfall patterns (Olusola et al., 2025). These changes have led to numerous environmental issues, including flash floods, landslides (Sule et al., 2024), and gully erosion, which have significantly damaged the land and impacted local communities (World Bank, 2022). The shift in rainfall has further aggravated problems such as desertification and soil erosion, leading to large areas becoming unproductive and threatening the livelihoods of agricultural dependents (Onyekuru & Marchant, 2016).

Socioeconomic elements further heighten the region's susceptibility. Environmental alterations have intensified economic inequality, fostering increased insecurity and displacement (Adekoya et al., 2025). Flooding has particularly devastated farmland and livelihoods, worsening food insecurity (Magaji & Musa, 2024). Additionally, recent events have resulted in the displacement of around 400,000 individuals (International Organisation for Migration, 2024). These difficulties emphasise the urgent necessity for effective strategies to build climate resilience in Northwest Nigeria.

Nature-based Solutions refer to actions that safeguard, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems to tackle societal challenges effectively and adaptively, thus providing benefits for human well-being and biodiversity simultaneously (International Union for Conservation of Nature, 2024). NbS include a variety of interventions, such as reforestation, wetland restoration, sustainable agriculture, and integrated watershed management. The goal of these methods is to harness the natural capacities of ecosystems to mitigate climate impacts, promote biodiversity, and support sustainable livelihoods.

Numerous initiatives have been launched to advocate for NbS in Northwest Nigeria. Projects centred on integrated watershed management aim to remedy extensive watershed degradation through sustainable land management techniques and restoration of damaged areas (Global Program on Nature-Based Solutions for Climate, 2024). Furthermore, efforts to bolster resilience against climate and security threats involve enhancing access to climate and security information (Magaji et al., 2022), encouraging climate-smart livelihoods, and reinforcing community-based natural resource management systems (Climate Diplomacy, 2024).

Despite ongoing efforts, the implementation of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) in the region encounters various obstacles. Constraints related to financial resources, lack of technical expertise, and ineffective institutional frameworks impede the expansion of NbS initiatives and youth migration (Magaji & Adamu, 2011). Additionally, there is a pressing need for increased community involvement and education to promote the sustainability and success of these solutions. Tackling these issues necessitates collaborative actions among government bodies, NGOs, local communities, and international partners to create and execute context-specific NbS strategies that are culturally relevant and economically feasible.

2. Literature Review

Conceptual Review: Nature-based Solutions (NbS): The United Nations Environment Programme and Environmental Audit (UNEP/EA, 2022) presents a thorough explanation of nature-based solutions, defining them as a "wide array of actions aimed at protecting, sustainably managing, and restoring natural or modified ecosystems, effectively addressing societal challenges while simultaneously enhancing human well-being, ecosystem services, and resilience benefits." This definition emphasises the diverse aspects of NbS, highlighting their ability to address various societal issues while enhancing both ecological and human welfare.

In a similar vein, Seddon et al. (2014) offer a fundamental definition of NbS, stating that they consist of "actions to safeguard, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems that effectively and adaptively respond to societal challenges, while also providing human well-being, ecosystem services, and resilience benefits." This definition underscores the adaptive nature of NbS, emphasising their capacity to adjust and respond to evolving environmental circumstances. It also highlights the interconnectedness between human well-being and ecological health, acknowledging that robust ecosystems are vital for human advancement.

Conversely, Held & Soden (2020) provide a definition of "climate" rather than NbS, characterising it as "the long-term average weather conditions at a specific location, typically averaged over 30 years, encompassing temperature, precipitation, humidity, sunshine, wind, and atmospheric pressure." While this definition is essential for grasping the context in which NbS function, it does not directly pertain to the concept of nature-based solutions. Instead, it establishes a crucial foundation for evaluating the effects of climate change and the role of NbS in alleviating those effects.

By synthesising these definitions, nature-based solutions can be defined as proactive strategies designed to protect, preserve, conserve, or sustain ecosystems, acknowledging their intrinsic worth and ability to provide vital services to society. This definition covers a wide range of actions, from ecosystem restoration efforts to sustainable management practices, all aimed at enhancing resilience and fostering human welfare.

Empirical Review

Raymond et al. (2017) conducted a study examining the feasibility of implementing NbS in mountainous catchments to alleviate the negative impacts of climate change, particularly focusing on drought-related declines in streamflow. The results of this research indicate that well-planned NbS interventions can considerably improve water availability during droughts. Enhancements in water retention and streamflow regulation are natural solutions that bolster water security and ecosystem resilience in mountainous areas.

Building on the theme of resilience, Frantzeskaki et al. (2019) conducted a meta-analysis evaluating the climate adaptation and mitigation effectiveness of hybrid engineering-natural coastal defence strategies. This comprehensive evaluation contrasts the efficacy of these hybrid methods with traditional complex infrastructures and reveals that hybrid solutions outperform conventional approaches in climate adaptation and mitigation. The findings of this study highlight the importance of incorporating natural elements into coastal protection strategies, stressing the potential for synergy between engineered and natural systems.

Van der Jagt et al. (2017) investigate the integration of NbS into spatial planning and policy frameworks for addressing climate change. They identify significant challenges and opportunities related to mainstreaming NbS across various governance levels, offering important insights for policymakers aiming to incorporate nature-based solutions into their planning frameworks. The authors emphasise effective practices for the successful execution of nature-based solutions (NbS), providing a guide for their integration. Nesshöver et al. (2017) present a thorough bibliographic analysis of the link between NbS and climate resilience. Their research identifies emerging trends, essential thematic areas, and knowledge gaps, providing critical insights for future research directions.

By mapping the current academic landscape and identifying areas that require further exploration, this study facilitates the growth of both the science and application of NbS. Boelee et al. (2017), in their article "How Cities Are Using Nature-Based Solutions to Tackle Floods," examine the rising trend of urban centres employing NbS to confront escalating flood hazards. Their paper showcases compelling case studies from multiple cities, highlighting the practical uses and substantial advantages of NbS in urban flood management. By presenting actual examples, the authors illustrate the ability of nature-based solutions to boost urban resilience and lessen flood effects.

The research conducted by Sabiu and Magaji (2024) focused on the effects of oil extraction and climate change in Nigeria's Niger Delta area. This study aimed to outline the socio-economic profiles of respondents, evaluate the level of environmental degradation, and assess the impacts of climate change in the area. Using a multi-stage sampling method, the researchers purposefully selected two states and gathered primary data, which were then analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The results indicated that most respondents were male, between the ages of 25 and 39, married Christians with diverse business activities and had a primary level education. Moreover, the study found that a notable percentage of respondents (45.3%) agreed that oil extraction leads to environmental degradation in the Niger Delta. The majority of respondents reported that climate change negatively impacts their agricultural productivity and fishing endeavours. The evaluation of oil spills revealed that 28.3% of respondents strongly agreed that regular oil spills consistently harm the area. As a result, many individuals in the region have shifted to non-farming livelihood activities. Additionally, 41.51% of respondents strongly confirmed experiencing oil spills in their vicinity, 18.87% strongly agreed that human error causes oil spills, and 11.32% strongly concurred.

Theoretical Framework

Political ecology theory serves as a valuable lens for examining the intricate connections between environmental shifts and socio-political frameworks. This theory recognises that environmental issues, including climate change, are deeply intertwined with the political and economic circumstances in which they arise. Political ecology examines how power relations, resource control, and economic motivations influence environmental outcomes and shape responses to ecological challenges. Political ecology highlights several fundamental concepts, including Power Dynamics, where the concept of power is essential. The theory analyses how power relationships at different scales, from local to global, affect resource access and environmental management decision-making. In Nigeria, the power distribution among various stakeholders, including the government, multinational corporations, and local communities, profoundly influences the handling of climate change impacts. Resource

Control: Political ecology examines who governs natural resources and how this governance shapes environmental and social outcomes.

In Nigeria, the dominance of oil resources by multinational corporations and the government has led to considerable environmental degradation, especially in the Niger Delta, and has affected the country's susceptibility to climate change. The emphasis on oil production has also obstructed the development of sustainable methods that could alleviate climate change. Economic Interests: Economic frameworks and motivations significantly influence environmental policies and practices. In Nigeria, the strong dependency on oil exports has established economic incentives that contradict environmental sustainability. The economic advantages of oil extraction have frequently overshadowed the long-term environmental and social repercussions, resulting in insufficient actions to combat climate change.

The theory of political ecology is particularly pertinent to analysing climate change in Nigeria, as it sheds light on the socio-political and economic factors that heighten the nation's vulnerability. Nigeria's heavy reliance on oil production within its political economy significantly affects its environmental sustainability. The Niger Delta region, for instance, has suffered considerable ecological damage from oil spills, gas flaring, and deforestation, primarily driven by the interests of both the Nigerian government and multinational oil companies (Sabiu & Magaji, 2024). Research conducted by Smith and Wandel (2006) illustrates how the political and economic agendas linked to oil extraction in Nigeria have resulted in environmental harm and the marginalisation of local populations, increasing their susceptibility to climate change impacts. The emphasis on oil has led to the sidelining of other important sectors, such as agriculture, which are vital for the livelihoods of countless Nigerians and are particularly vulnerable to climate change.

Political ecology further highlights the governance challenges that contribute to Nigeria's susceptibility to climate change. Ineffective environmental governance, corruption, and poor institutional capacity have impeded the country's capability to implement and enforce climate adaptation and mitigation initiatives. Additionally, political ecology emphasises the impact of global economic frameworks on determining local environmental outcomes. Nigeria's role as a significant oil producer in the global market means that international energy demands and price shifts directly affect its economic stability and ability to tackle climate change. The global movement toward climate action, which includes a transition to renewable energy, poses both challenges and opportunities for Nigeria as it seeks to harmonise economic growth with environmental sustainability.

The political ecology framework provides insightful perspectives on understanding the complex repercussions of climate change in Nigeria. This theory offers a critical perspective for examining the broader socio-political and economic contexts that shape Nigeria's response to climate challenges. It emphasises the necessity of addressing both immediate and structural factors contributing to Nigeria's vulnerability, which can inform more effective and equitable climate policies and strategies (Ismail et al., 2019).

3. Methodology

This research employed a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative strategies to gain a thorough understanding of the obstacles and challenges in applying Nature-based Solutions (NbS) in Northwest Nigeria. This methodological choice

was driven by the intricate socio-political, economic, and environmental facets of NbS, requiring both statistical data and contextual understanding for meaningful analysis.

Research Design: The study employed a cross-sectional design, which facilitated the collection of data at a single point in time from a large population sample. This was enhanced by qualitative approaches that captured personal experiences, perceptions, and socio-cultural factors affecting NbS adoption. The quantitative component produced statistical data regarding the prevalence of identified challenges, while the qualitative aspect added depth to these findings through narratives from stakeholders and community members. This combination of methods ensured the robustness, validity, and reliability of the results.

Study Area: The research was conducted in Northwest Nigeria, specifically in Sokoto, Zamfara, and Katsina States. These states were intentionally chosen due to their vulnerability to climate change, widespread environmental degradation, and socio-political issues such as insecurity and poverty, which directly affect the implementation of NbS. The region is situated within the Sudan savanna ecological zone, containing semi-arid regions that rely heavily on agriculture and livestock farming. Environmental challenges like desertification, gully erosion, flooding, and land degradation make this area particularly appropriate for examining NbS interventions.

Population of the Study: The study's target population included individuals aged 18 and older living in the chosen states. This group encompasses farmers, pastoralists, traders, community leaders, youth, women, and other communities whose livelihoods and well-being are significantly affected by environmental changes. Moreover, institutional stakeholders such as government agencies, NGOs, and traditional institutions were included in the qualitative aspect of the research.

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques: The Taro Yamane (1967) formula was utilised to calculate a suitable sample size of 700 participants for the survey. Due to the extensive and dispersed nature of the population in the study area, a multi-stage sampling approach was implemented:

- i. Purposive sampling was employed to select Sokoto, Zamfara, and Katsina States based on their relevance to the study's objectives.
- ii. Cluster sampling was utilised to categorise the states into Local Government Areas (LGAs) to ensure geographical representation.
- iii. Simple random sampling was then applied to select respondents within each cluster, guaranteeing that every household or individual had an equal opportunity to be chosen.

This methodology minimised sampling bias and ensured that the sample was representative.

Data Collection Methods: Two primary tools were employed:

Structured Questionnaires – administered to 700 participants to gather quantitative data on perceived obstacles and challenges to Nature-based Solutions (NbS). The questionnaire consisted of both closed-ended and Likert-scale questions to facilitate statistical analysis.

Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) – conducted with selected stakeholders, including farmers' associations, women's groups, youth representatives, government officials, and NGO personnel. FGDs delved into detailed perspectives on insecurity, poverty, awareness, and governance related to NbS.

Trained research assistants fluent in the local languages (Hausa and Fulfulde) were hired to ensure effective communication and data gathering.

Validity and Reliability of Instruments: To ensure validity, the instruments were reviewed by experts in environmental management and sustainable development from the University of Abuja. A pilot study involving 30 participants from outside the study areas was conducted to refine any unclear questions. The reliability of the questionnaire was evaluated using the Cronbach's Alpha test, which produced a coefficient exceeding 0.7, indicating strong internal consistency.

Data Analysis Techniques: Quantitative Data - Data obtained through the questionnaires were coded and entered into SPSS Version 27 for analysis. Descriptive statistics (frequency distributions, percentages, and means) were used to summarise socio-demographic variables and barriers to NbS. Inferential statistics, such as Chi-square tests, were conducted to examine associations between demographic factors (e.g., income, education) and perceived barriers.

Qualitative Data: FGDs were recorded, transcribed, and analysed thematically. Thematic coding was guided by key research questions, facilitating the identification of recurring themes such as insecurity, poverty, and lack of awareness. Direct quotes from participants were included to illustrate the findings.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval was obtained from the University of Abuja Sustainable Development Centre Research Ethics Committee. Informed consent was secured from all participants, and respondents were assured of their anonymity, confidentiality, and the voluntary nature of their involvement. Care was taken to handle sensitive topics regarding security and livelihoods to prevent psychological distress.

4. Data Presentation, Results, and Discussion

4.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Out of the 700 questionnaires distributed, 684 were returned valid for analysis, representing a 97.7% response rate. Table 1 presents the key socio-demographic variables of respondents.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n = 684)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	427	62.4
	Female	257	37.6
Age	18–29 years	152	22.2
	30–44 years	311	45.5
	45–59 years	169	24.7
	60 years+	52	7.6
Education	No formal education	198	28.9
	Primary	172	25.1
	Secondary	192	28.1
	Tertiary	122	17.9
Occupation	Farming	309	45.2
	Pastoralism	97	14.2
	Trading	134	19.6
	Civil service/Other	144	21.0

The data indicate that most respondents were male (62.4%), aged between 30 and 44 years (45.5%), and engaged in farming (45.2%), reflecting the agrarian nature of Northwest Nigeria. Nearly 54% had only primary or no formal education, which may influence awareness and adoption of NbS.

4.2 Barriers to Implementing Nature-based Solutions (NbS)

Respondents were asked to identify the primary barriers hindering NbS adoption. Results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Barriers to NbS Implementation (n = 684)

Barrier	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Insecurity and Conflict	246	36.0
Poverty and Limited Resources	344	50.3
Lack of Awareness/Knowledge	94	13.7
Total	684	100.0

Poverty emerged as the most significant barrier (50.3%), followed by insecurity and conflict (36%) and lack of awareness (13.7%).

4.3 Inferential Statistical Tests

A Chi-square test of independence was conducted to examine whether socio-demographic characteristics (education, income, and occupation) were associated with perceived barriers.

Table 3: Chi-Square Tests for Association Between Demographics and Perceived Barriers

Variable	χ^2 Value	df	p-value	Association
Education × Barrier	21.74	6	0.001	Significant
Income × Barrier	18.92	4	0.002	Significant
Occupation × Barrier	8.67	3	0.034	Significant

The findings indicate that education, income, and occupation are significantly related to perceptions of barriers ($p < 0.05$). For instance, those without formal education were more inclined to mention "lack of awareness" as a hindrance, whereas poverty was the predominant concern among low-income households. Farmers and pastoralists emphasised insecurity to a greater extent than civil servants and traders.

4.4 Insights from Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)

The FGDs offered a deeper understanding of the statistical outcomes. Three key themes emerged:

1. Insecurity as an Obstacle

“The primary issue is insecurity. Bandits and kidnappers have forced us to abandon our farms. How can we consider tree planting or watershed restoration when we cannot reach our land?” (Male farmer, Zamfara FGD).

2. Poverty and Resource Limitations

“Even if we desire to plant trees or engage in soil conservation, we lack the financial resources or tools. Poverty is the greatest adversary to environmental preservation.” (Female trader, Sokoto FGD).

3. Lack of Awareness and Knowledge

“Many individuals here do not even grasp what Nature-based Solutions entail. They view tree planting or water management as tasks for the government, not their responsibility.” (Youth leader, Katsina FGD).

4.5 Confirmation of Findings

The quantitative data indicated that poverty (50.3%) and insecurity (36%) were the main barriers. Concurrently, qualitative insights reinforced these results by illustrating how armed

conflicts displace farmers and how poverty inhibits the adoption of NbS practices. Although lack of awareness was ranked lowest (13.7%), it was also apparent in the FGDs, particularly among participants with minimal or no formal education.

The combined outcomes thus suggest a complex challenge, where economic, security, and knowledge gaps interact with one another, undermining the success of NbS.

4.6 Interpretation of Findings

The findings support the political ecology theory, which posits that environmental issues cannot be separated from political and economic systems. Insecurity in Northwest Nigeria, fueled by armed conflicts and competition for resources, directly obstructs environmental initiatives. Likewise, poverty and inadequate institutional support limit the financial and technical capabilities of communities to adopt NbS.

These results are consistent with Onyekuru & Marchant (2016), who found that socioeconomic vulnerability exacerbates environmental degradation in Nigeria, and Frantzeskaki et al. (2019), who highlighted that institutional capacity is crucial for the successful adoption of NbS.

Therefore, the implementation of NbS in Northwest Nigeria cannot be effective without concurrently addressing poverty alleviation, enhancing security, and promoting environmental awareness. The evidence strongly indicates that NbS should be integrated with broader livelihood support and peacebuilding efforts.

5. Conclusion

This research explored the obstacles impeding the implementation of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) in Northwest Nigeria, utilising a mixed-methods approach. The results showed that poverty (50.3%), insecurity and conflict (36%), and lack of awareness (13.7%) are the most substantial challenges to the adoption of NbS in Sokoto, Zamfara, and Katsina States. Chi-square findings further suggested that socio-demographic variables such as education, income, and occupation have a significant effect on perceptions of barriers. Qualitative findings bolstered these results, with participants underscoring the interconnectedness of insecurity, poverty, and low awareness as mutually reinforcing issues.

Aligned with political ecology theory, the study concludes that NbS cannot be scalable in Northwest Nigeria without tackling broader socioeconomic inequalities, security challenges, and institutional deficiencies. Addressing these barriers is vital for enhancing climate resilience, improving livelihoods, and ensuring sustainable environmental stewardship in vulnerable contexts.

6. Recommendations

1. Reinforce Policy and Institutional Frameworks – Both federal and state authorities should incorporate Nature-based Solutions (NbS) into climate change, agricultural, and rural development strategies to promote widespread implementation.

2. Enhance Security in Rural Areas – Efforts to improve security should focus on safeguarding agricultural lands and communities, enabling the secure application of NbS methods such as afforestation and watershed management.
3. Address Poverty Through Livelihood Support – Offer microloans, agricultural supplies, and skills training to strengthen community capabilities in adopting NbS as a part of initiatives aimed at poverty alleviation.
4. Encourage Community Awareness and Environmental Education – Initiate community-driven awareness campaigns to boost understanding and ownership of NbS programs, particularly in rural and low-literacy regions.
5. Promote Multi-Stakeholder Collaboration – Collaborative efforts among governments, non-governmental organisations, traditional leaders, and international stakeholders should be undertaken to gather resources and coordinate NbS actions.
6. Enhance Local Capacity – Improve the skills of extension agents, local non-profits, and youth organisations to act as advocates for the implementation of NbS.

Value Addition to Knowledge

This research contributes to the growing literature on NbS in Africa by providing context-specific empirical data from Northwest Nigeria. This area is particularly susceptible to the dual challenges of climate change and insecurity. While many studies have underscored the capability of NbS to bolster resilience, few have methodically examined the obstacles to their adoption in fragile and conflict-affected environments. By combining both quantitative and qualitative data, this research illustrates how poverty, insecurity, and lack of awareness interconnectedly hinder NbS, providing a more detailed understanding of the political ecology surrounding environmental management in Nigeria. The results also yield evidence-based insights for policymakers to craft integrated strategies that link NbS with peacebuilding and poverty reduction efforts.

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